

UDC 338.43.02
JEL E23;J43;L15.

ROLE OF STANDARDIZATION IN INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS IN THE WORLD MARKET

РОЛЬ СТАНДАРТИЗАЦИИ В ПОВЫШЕНИИ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ СЕЛЬСКОХОЗЯЙСТВЕННОЙ ПРОДУКЦИИ НА МИРОВОМ РЫНКЕ

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Abstract. The article analyzes deeper study of many foreign and local economist scientists, analyzing the dynamics and per capita changes in the mainstream agricultural products of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2000–2016. Also, the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan has provided scientifically substantiated proposals and recommendations based on the results of the dynamic change, taking into account the ongoing reforms in the development of the agricultural economy. Many scientific works will be a major factor in theoretical and practical scientific study of the problems of agricultural product market efficiency in the modernization of the economy, contributing to the agrarian–economic science. In spite of the fact that reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan on the practical aspects of organizing, managing and increasing the effectiveness of the fruit and vegetable and grape sub–complex at the stage of economic liberalization, the above–mentioned researches did not adequately investigate the existing problems. In this paper have been used such research methodologies as: economic analysis, statistical grouping, comparative and systematic analysis, logical, monographic, etc.

Аннотация. В статье анализируется углубленное изучение многих зарубежных и местных ученых–экономистов, анализирующих динамику и изменения на душу населения в основной сельскохозяйственной продукции Республики Узбекистан на 2000–2016 годы. Кроме того, Правительство Республики Узбекистан предоставило научно обоснованные предложения и рекомендации, основанные на результатах динамических изменений, с учетом проводимых реформ в развитии сельскохозяйственной экономики. Многие научные труды станут основным фактором теоретического и практического научного исследования проблем эффективности рынка сельскохозяйственной продукции в модернизации экономики, способствующей аграрно–экономической науке. Несмотря на то, что реформы в Республике Узбекистан по практическим аспектам организации, управления и повышения эффективности плодовоовощного и виноградного подкомплексов на этапе экономической либерализации, вышеупомянутые исследования не проводили адекватного расследования существующие проблемы. В этой статье были использованы такие исследовательские методологии, как: экономический анализ, статистическая группировка, сравнительный и систематический анализ, логический, монографический и т. д.

Keywords: dynamic indicators, social stability, food security, action strategy, structural change, infrastructure.

Ключевые слова: динамические показатели, социальная стабильность, продовольственная безопасность, стратегия действий, структурные изменения, инфраструктура.

Introduction

In any developed or developing country, the development of the national economy will depend on the social protection of the population, the strengthening of social stability and, among other factors, the environmental safety of food products. Food security is largely dependent on the level of development of agriculture, quantitative indicators of production, processing conditions, storage, agrotechnological processes, quality of network products, ie the level of availability of products on the world standards.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoev “On the strategy of action for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan” (1) the “Modernization and Accelerated Development of Agriculture”, as set forth in paragraph 3.3 of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

–deepening of structural reforms and continuous development of agricultural production, further strengthening of food security of the country, expansion of production of ecologically clean products, considerable increase of export potential of the agrarian sector;

–to reduce the area of cotton and cereal grains, to further improve the area of cultivation, placement of potatoes, vegetables, food and oil crops, as well as new intensive gardens and vineyards;

–Implementation of investment projects on construction, reconstruction and modernization of new processing enterprises equipped with the latest high tech equipment for the production of semi-finished products and finished products as well as packaging products for deep processing of agricultural products;

–it is planned to further strengthen the infrastructure of storage, transportation and sale of agricultural products, agrochemical, financial and other modern market services..

This, in turn, confirms the necessity of scientifically-based development and development of the system of agricultural production in the country’s agro-industrial complex on the basis of world standards, production, processing, delivery to consumers.

Literature review

Theoretical-methodological foundations of the issues of improving the efficiency of socio-economic development and financing of agriculture from foreign scientists L. Tsfu, Ts. Fan, L. Chjou [1], L. V. Agarkova [2] I. B. Buzdalov [3], I. Sandu [4], I. G. Ushachev [5], Fruit and vegetable and grape market problems were analyzed by foreign scientists such as N. Popov [6]. From Uzbek scientists to the role of agriculture in improving the wellbeing of the population and development of A. Abduganiev [7] On the improvement of economic relations in the development of grain growing in the Republic of Uzbekistan G. Khudratov [8], the problems of agricultural development and the practical and theoretical significance of the reforms being undertaken to address them A. M. Juraev, R. H. Husanov [9], increasing the cost-effectiveness of production at agricultural enterprises of various forms of ownership has been studied in the scientific studies of A. Kh. Burhonov [10].

Main part

Currently, the Republic of Uzbekistan has a number of challenges to improving agricultural production and processing enterprises, maintaining agricultural products at the market level, supply

and sales, improving the quality and competitiveness of products. These include, but are not limited to, non-compliance of national standards with international standards, such as quality management, product storage and public procurement, in the process of supplying agricultural products to consumers grown or refined by farms, processing enterprises

- lack of infrastructure for agricultural production, storage and sale;
- changes in the volumes of products produced by agricultural enterprises during the year;
- decrease in availability of agricultural products in winter months, especially in urban areas, increase of their prices, etc.

In order to overcome these problems, macro-spatial use of limited resources and the state's regulatory mechanisms for the socio-economic development of the regions are required. Development of agro-industrial complex in Uzbekistan is one of the priorities of economic reforms. Its implementation will greatly reduce the unemployment rate and solve social problems. For example, creating only one worker in the canning sector of fruits and vegetables provides 5–6 jobs in fruit and vegetable production.

As a result of structural reforms in agriculture in Uzbekistan, and the transfer of cotton fields to fruit and vegetable production, these crops have grown significantly. At the same time, such sectors as agriculture, fruits and vegetables, horticulture, viticulture and animal husbandry have been developing at a rapid pace. In 2015, 12 million 592 thousand tons of vegetables and potatoes, 1 million 850 thousand tons of melons, 1 million 556 thousand tons of grapes and 2 million 731 thousand tons of fruit have been grown.

In the production of agricultural products and their export to the domestic and foreign markets, significant measures are being undertaken throughout the country. As a result, agricultural production grows every year (Table).

Table.

THE MAIN TYPES OF AGRICULTURAL CROPS (ts / ha)

<i>Indicators</i>	2000	2005	2010	2015	2016
Total forage and groats grain	28.2	40.7	44.2	45.3	45.0
Cotton	21.8	25.3	25.4	25.9	23.4
Potatoes	129.3	170.3	194.9	219.1	225.1
Vegetables, total	183.8	215.8	252.5	271.0	271.1
Food of melon	132.4	169.1	192.6	203.6	209.4
Fruits and berries ^p	56.9	62.3	92.6	128.1	134.1
Grape	63.1	64.7	90.8	133.1	141.9

Source: Data of State Statistics Committee of Uzbekistan.

According to the data of Table, in 2000 crops and grains grew by 28.2 centner per hectare of total crop yield, cotton — 21.8 tons, potatoes — 129.3 tons, fruit and berries — 56.9 centners per hectare. and grapes equaled to 63.1 centners, in 2016 the production of these crops and the implementation of the necessary agrotechnical works resulted in an increase in the yield of agricultural crops by an average of 1 hectare of grain and cereal crops to 16.8 centners, cotton — to 1.6 centners, potatoes — 95.8 centners, vegetables — 87.3 centners, melons — 77.0 centners, fruits — 77.2 centners, grapes — 78.8 percent.

This allows for a continuous increase in prices for seasonal seasonal supply of the population with major types of agricultural products, expanding exports of these products, and maintaining

price stability. At the same time, agriculture is witnessing the rapid growth of such sectors as fruit and vegetable, horticulture, viticulture and animal husbandry.

When analyzing the per capita agricultural output in Uzbekistan, it can be seen that positive results have been achieved (Figure).

Figure shows that in 2016, per capita production of agricultural products in 2016 will be as follows: grain — 100 kg, potatoes — 63 kg, vegetables — 247 kg, melons — 46 kg, fruits — 64 kg grapes — 30 kg, meat — 34 kg milk — 158 kg and egg — 142 units. This, in turn, is the result of timely consistent implementation of measures aimed at raising the level of agricultural production in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Source: Data of State Statistics Committee of Uzbekistan.

Figure. The main agricultural products of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2000–2016 (kg, egg–pieces)

According to the results of the analysis, the main reason for achieving such positive results is the implementation of targeted measures aimed at gradual optimization of the structure of cultivated areas by expanding the area of food crops, as well as the implementation of specific measures in livestock farming. It is advisable to consider the priority tasks of stimulating the increase in the number of bird poultry.

Conclusion

In summary, more than 98 percent of all agricultural production in the Republic of Uzbekistan is worth \$ 4.3 million. hectare of irrigated lands, improvement of the land use system is one of the important directions of the agrarian sector reforming.

To improve the export base of the agrarian sector in the country's economy, to increase the production capacity and the quality of agricultural raw materials

–development of social infrastructure in rural areas;

–further support of the forms of cooperation of agricultural production and processing industry, multisectoral farming enterprises by the state;

–Improvement of organizational directions of the system of qualitative storage of agricultural products with the study of climatic conditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, reduction of cost savings on the basis of modern equipment, technology saving of warehouses, and also their intensification on modern technological basis and increase of export.

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*Работа поступила
в редакцию 11.09.2017 г.*

*Принята к публикации
14.09.2017 г.*

Ссылка для цитирования:

Imomov J. Role of standardization in increasing the competitiveness of agricultural products in the world market // Бюллетень науки и практики. Электрон. журн. 2017. №10 (23). С. 244-249. Режим доступа: <http://www.bulletennauki.com/imomov> (дата обращения 15.10.2017).

Cite as (APA):

Imomov, J. (2017). Role of standardization in increasing the competitiveness of agricultural products in the world market. *Bulletin of Science and Practice*, (10), 244-249